

Level of Awareness and use of Modern Family Planning Methods by Young Women of Reproductive Age in Sagbama Local Government Area, Bayelsa State

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Abstract

The study determined the level of awareness and use of modern family planning methods by women of reproductive age in Sagbama Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study ascertained the awareness of modern family planning methods by the respondents; identified their source of information on modern birth-control methods; determined whether the respondents made use of modern family planning methods; and identified the barriers to the use of modern birth control methods. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. Questionnaire was the instrument for data collection. The questionnaires were administered to 80 respondents from the 163 young women that were registered at the post-natal unit of the general hospital and health center in Sagbama local government area. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages were used for data analysis. Background information of the respondents showed that 45% of them were married, 46.25% were farmers and 38.75% of them had only secondary education. The result showed that majority of the respondents were aware of modern family planning methods such as use of condom (83.75%), contraceptive pills (70.0%) and contraceptive injections (62.50%). Result also showed that the respondents' source of information on family planning was mainly from hospital and health centres (51.25%), mass media (42.50%) and community meetings (38.75%). About 37.50% of the respondents adopted modern methods of birth control such as contraceptive pills (27.50%), condoms (27.50%), contraceptive patch (25.00%), spermicides (18.75%), contraceptive injections (16.25%) and cervical cap (12.50%), while little and no adoption was recorded for the use of intra-uterine devices (1.25%) and vasectomy (0.0%) respectively. The major factors militating against the women's use of modern family planning methods were their husbands' disapproval (64%), fear of side effects (53%), poor knowledge of methods (41%), limited supply (34%), personal objection and religious barrier (41%), high cost of some of the methods (26%), cultural barrier (19%) and lack of family planning clinics (11%). It was recommended that modern birth-control methods be made available and affordable to women through their local health centres to promote their use. In addition, interventions that will include husbands should be organized to reduce opposition and barriers to the use of modern birth-control methods.

Keywords: *Birth-control, Family planning, Reproductive age, Fertility, Contraceptive use*

Introduction

Population growth has been a problematic issue all over the world especially in developing countries (Anyanwu, Ezegbe & Eskay, 2013). There is growing evidence that uncontrolled population growth has triggered off economic problems, rising cost of living and a higher level of consumption

which has resulted in changing patterns of land use, increased energy use and the depletion of natural resources, with signs of climate change and environmental degradation more visible than ever before (WHO, 2014; United-Nations, 2015). The United Nations' population estimate (2017)

showed that the world population is at over 7.7 billion and projections indicate that it will reach 10 billion in 2055. Africa, the second most populated continent has a population estimate of over 1.3 billion. Nigeria which happens to be the most populous country in Africa has a population estimate of over 200 million persons and is projected to have over 410 million by 2050 (United-Nations, 2017). WHO (2014) has identified that the key to slowing unsustainable population growth and its negative impact on the economy, environment, as well as national and regional development efforts to be family planning.

Family planning implies the ability of individuals and couples to anticipate and attain desired number of children by spacing and timing their births (Omolase, Faturoti, & Omolase, 2009). The introduction of modern contraceptive techniques over the recent decade and the increasing availability of safer and more effective methods of preventing pregnancy have permitted people around the world to exercise their choice and make responsible decisions with respect to their reproduction and enjoy the benefits of family planning (Nansseu, Nchnda, Katte, Nchagnouot & Nguetsa, 2015). World Reports have shown that family planning methods are used by the majority of married women in almost all regions of the world, however, the use is much lower in Africa (32%) compared to the other major regions in the world such as Oceania (58%) and Northern America (75%) (United-Nations, 2017). According to the Population Reference Bureau (2018), modern contraceptive use in Nigeria is at 18%. This implies that many women of reproductive age in Nigeria may still be utilizing the traditional and less effective methods of contraception or use no method at all. Available evidence shows that family planning has the potential of ensuring optimum spacing between births, reducing maternal and child mortality, improving the lives of women and children, increasing the ability to meet household economic needs, and slowing population growth, thereby contributing effectively to the socio-

economic development of the country (WHO, 2014; Falode & Akintaro, 2014; Ajayi, Adeniyi & Akpan, 2018).

Problem Statement

Despite the growing awareness of benefits accrued to birth-control and its role in reducing maternal and neonatal mortality, the acceptance and utilization of contraceptive methods is still at a low level, particularly in unindustrialized nations and among the rural populace (Ndikom, Ojo & Ogbeye, 2018). United Nations (2017) highlighted that there are large gaps in the proportion of demand for modern family planning methods (MFPM) in countries where overall modern birth-control methods use is low or where many couples rely on traditional family planning methods (Peltzer, Akintade & Pengpid, 2011; Falode & Akintaro, 2014). Ajayi et al., (2018), reported that of the current users of family planning methods as 44.30% were using a traditional method such as withdrawal, periodic abstinence and lactational amenorrhoea. Again, there are remarkable socio-cultural and ethno-religious variations in the different communities that constitute the Nigerian nation, which affect the use of contraceptives among women and bring about disparity in the results obtained at the national level. There is therefore, the need to obtain data at the rural levels in order to understand the various social, cultural and religious factors that are peculiar to individual communities in Nigeria, especially in Sagbama LGA of Bayelsa State.

Objectives of the study

The broad objective of this study was to investigate the awareness and use of various modern family planning methods by women of reproductive age in Sagbama local government area, Bayelsa state. The specific objectives of the study were to:

1. identify the awareness of different modern family planning methods by women of reproductive age in Sagbama local government area, Bayelsa State.
2. determine the women's source of

- information on modern family planning methods.
3. ascertain the use of modern family planning methods by women of reproductive age in Sagbama
 4. identify the factors that prevented the women from using the modern family planning method in Sagbama local government area, Bayelsa State.

Methodology

Research design: The study adopted a descriptive survey design. Descriptive research is used to describe characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied at a given period of time with the aim of generalizing the finding among the population under study (Shields & Rangarajan, 2013).

Population: The study population was 163 women of reproductive age registered at the post-natal unit of the General hospital Sagbama and Sagbama health centre, at the time of the study. Sagbama is one of the eight Local Government Areas in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Its headquarters is in the town of Sagbama. It has an area of 945 km² and a population of 187,146 according to the 2006 census. Sagbama LGA is under Bayelsa West Senatorial District. Sagbama LGA was considered because it is a rural area where studies on awareness and use of modern family planning methods have not been conducted.

Sample and sampling

Purposive sampling technique was used to select 80 women of reproductive age who gave their consent and were available at the time of study in the general hospital and health centre. Forty-five percent of the respondents were married, 46.25% were farmers and 38.75% had secondary education. Majority (87.50%) of the respondents were Christians, 62.50% had 1-3 children and 35.00% had 4-6 children. Fifty-five percent of the respondents used 3years birth interval and more than half (65.00%) preferred family size of 3-6 persons.

Method of data collection: A structured questionnaire titled 'Awareness and Use of Modern Family Planning Questionnaire' (AUFPPQ) was used to elicit information from the respondents over a period of four weeks. The questionnaire was made up of sections A to E. Section A contained items on the respondents' demographic characteristics. Section B was used to elicit data on awareness of modern family planning methods. In this section, the respondents were asked if they are aware of 13 modern methods of family planning. The response options were "yes" and "no". Section C was used to obtain data on the source of awareness information. Six items of the sources were presented, and the respondents were expected to tick as many options as were applicable to them. Section D was used to elicit data on the use of modern family planning methods. The respondents were given the option to tick as many of the family planning methods as they have used. Section E contained items on the factors that hinder the use of the methods. Ten factors were itemised, which the respondents were expected to tick as many as were applicable to them. The researchers administered the questionnaire on immunization days for easy accessibility. All the distributed questionnaires were collected, giving a 100% return rate.

Data analysis: Data were analysed using frequencies and percentages. The result are presented in tables, while, Bar chart was used to present data on factors that hinder the use of modern family planning methods.

Results

Table 1 presents data on the respondents' awareness of modern family planning methods. Majority (83.75%) of the women were aware of condom, 62.50% were aware of contraceptive injections and 70.0% were aware of contraceptive pills. Other methods include awareness of vagina diaphragm (30.00%), contraceptive patch (33.75%), emergency contraceptive pills (36.25%) and contraceptive rings (35.00%).

Table 1: Respondents' Awareness of Modern Birth-Control Methods

S/N	Methods of Family planning	F	%
1	Condom	67	83.75
2	Vagina Diaphragm	24	30.00
3	Spermicides	14	17.50
4	Cervical Cap	13	16.25
5	Intrauterine Devices	30	37.50
6	Contraceptive Injections	50	62.50
7	Contraceptive Pills	56	70.00
8	Contraceptive Patch	27	33.75
9	Contraceptive Rings	28	35.00
10	Emergency Contraceptive Pills	29	36.25
11	Vasectomy	17	21.25
12	Tubal Ligation	17	21.25
13	Implants	21	26.25

Table 2 shows the respondents' source of information on family planning. From the data, the major source of information was from hospital and health centres (51.25%), mass media (42.50%) and community

meetings (38.75%). Other sources of information include churches (36.25%), friends (18.75%) and extension programmes (18.75%).

Table 2: Respondents' Sources of Information on Family Planning Methods

S/N	Sources of Family Planning Information	F	%
1	Hospital And Health Centres	41	51.25
2	Community Meetings	31	38.75
3	Friends And Neighbours	15	18.75
4	Mass Media (Radio/Television, Billboard Advertisement)	34	42.50
5	Church Marriage Seminars/Counselling	29	36.25
6	Extension Programs	15	18.75

Table 3 shows the respondents' use of modern family planning methods. Up to 37.50% of the respondents adopted contraceptive pills, condoms (27.50%), contraceptive patch (25.00%), spermicides (18.75%), contraceptive injections (16.25%) and cervical cap (12.50%). Very few

respondents used the following family planning methods; emergency pills (11.25%), tubal ligation (6.25%), contraceptive rings (6.25%), vagina diaphragm (1.25%) and IUDs (1.25%). None of the respondents reported vasectomy use as their family planning option.

Table 3: Respondents’ use of modern birth-control methods

Fig 1 presents information on the barriers to the use of modern birth-control methods. Up to 64% of the respondents do not use modern birth-control methods because of husband’s disapproval, 53% due to fear of side effects, 41% due to poor knowledge of method,

38% as a result of inconvenience, 34% due to limited supply, 41% as a result of personal objection and religious barrier, 26% due to high cost, 19% due to cultural barrier and 11% due to lack of family planning clinics.

Fig 1: Barriers to the use of Modern family planning methods

Discussion

The study determined the awareness and use of various modern family planning methods by women of reproductive age in Sagbama, Bayelsa state. The findings in table 1 showed that there is high awareness of some of the modern family

planning methods like condom, contraceptive injections and contraceptive pills. This could be attributed to the level of publicity given

to the three methods in most of the health facilities in the area. Peltzer et al., (2011), showed that the level of awareness of family planning methods among female university students in Lesotho was high (98.3%). The findings of the study also support the work of Falode and Akintaro (2014) in four maternity centers in Olorunda Local Government Area of OsunState, Nigeria which shows that there is a general increase in the awareness of the benefits of various contraceptive measures.

Findings on table two showed that mothers' sources of information on modern family planning methods were mainly through hospitals/health centres, mass media, community meetings and church seminars/counselling. This shows similar result to the findings of Sreytouch (2008) that health centres and media were the main sources of information on family planning. Other studies by Ezonbodor-Akwagbe (2013); Ofonime and Ikibong (2016) and Upadhayay, Shah, Thapa, Ghimire and Dahal (2017), reported hospital, mobile clinics, television, radio, posters and newspaper as major sources of information on modern family planning methods. The implication of this result is that primary health care providers have a major role to play in improving couple's awareness and knowledge of modern family planning methods. In this regard, primary health care providers' knowledge and skills must be continuously enhanced and reinforced to deliver the right and sound advice about the use of modern family planning methods.

The result on table three also showed that modern family planning methods mostly used by the respondents were contraceptive pills, followed by condom and contraceptive patch. This agrees with the study by Sreytouch (2008) that showed pill as the most commonly used in the area. The findings also corroborates with the result from the studies of Peltzer et al., (2011); Tilahun et al., (2013) and Ofonime and Ikibong (2016) which showed that the most commonly used methods were condoms, pills, injectable, emergency contraceptive pills, female and male sterilization, and the intra-uterine

contraceptive device (IUCD). A noteworthy finding in this study is the low use of implants, suggesting that health facilities in the study area may have been unable to deliver this service.

Findings of this study as presented on the bar chart showed husbands' disapproval, fear of side effects, poor knowledge of the methods and personal objections as the main reasons for not using the modern methods of family planning. This is supported by Sreytouch (2008) who identified fear of side effects and desire for more children as reasons for not using modern methods of family planning. Similar result was also seen in a study by Upadhayay et al., (2017) that concluded that the main reason for not utilizing contraceptives was desires to have more children, followed by husband disapproval of contraceptive and fear of side effects of contraceptive methods. This finding also corroborates that of Nansseu et al., (2015) that reported difficult usage, side effects and ineffectiveness as some of the reasons why women were not satisfied with the method they are using. These barriers, therefore, have to be taken into consideration when carrying out education and communication programmes in order to enhance the use of modern birth-control methods especially in the rural settings.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Awareness of the existence and purpose of health support devices or services usually goes a long way to influence individuals' decisions to adopt such devices, however, such awareness is influenced by how much publicity and information is given about the product or services to those that need it. Awareness of the existence of modern birth-control methods was high especially for condoms, contraceptive injections, and pills. Their major sources of information on modern family planning methods were from hospital and health-centre, followed by mass media and community meetings. However, high awareness does not usually translate to high level of use, hence the use of the various modern methods of family planning was low in the study area. The most

highlighted hindrance to the use of modern methods of family planning was husbands' disapproval and fear of side effects, indicating the need for more family planning education that will target both husbands and wives.

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made.

1. It is important for health care providers, especially those working in pre and post-natal units of health facilities to continuously equip their patients with proper information about birth control. This will improve their knowledge and consequently adoption of these methods.
2. More counselling interventions on family planning that will include men should be organized by governmental and non-governmental organizations.
3. Studies by family planning experts and researchers on development of intervention programs aimed at addressing the existing barriers to the use of the methods should be carried out.

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